

EVALUATION OF THE USE OF RECYCLED CONCRETE POWDER (RCP) IN THE WORKABILITY AND COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF PORTLAND CEMENT PASTES

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Abstract

Construction is one of the industries with the greatest environmental impact in the world, highlighting the emission of CO₂ and the generation of waste. In this sense, reducing, reusing, and recycling materials is a sustainable alternative to mitigate this problem. This study aims to evaluate the use of Recycled Concrete Powder (RCP) as a substitute for Portland cement, considering two sources of RCP: demolition and laboratory waste. Cement pastes containing 10, 20, and 30% RCP from both sources were prepared. Workability was evaluated through the mini-slump test. Compressive strength was determined for 7 and 28 days. The modulus of elasticity and microstructure were analyzed after 28 days. With increasing substitution of Portland cement by RCP, there is a downward trend in the properties evaluated, regardless of source. However, the compressive strength of 10% RCP and reference was statistically similar, indicating that the use of lower proportions is feasible. Using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), various hydration products, such as ettringite (AFt), calcium hydroxide (CH), and calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H) were observed in all pastes containing RCP. The source of RCP does not affect the properties evaluated, and its use can be indistinct.

1. Introduction

Cement-based materials are the most widely used in the construction industry and their demand is growing every year [1,2]. Therefore, ways to improve the performance of these materials are being investigated, both technically and in regards to reducing their environmental impact, which is mainly associated with the production of Portland cement [3]. It is estimated that Portland cement requires 125 kW/h of electricity and emits 800 kg of CO₂ during its production [4]. As such, recent investigations have investigated recycled concrete powder (RCP) as a supplementary cementitious material (SCM) [5-7].

The RCP comes from the production of recycled concrete aggregate (RCA), considering particles smaller than 150 µm [8]. However, it is recommended that the particle size of the RCP be close to the granulometry of Portland cement, in order to improve its reactivity [6,9]. Therefore, it is suggested that RCP be finely ground to obtain adequate performance in cement-

based materials [10]. Various studies have shown the potential of using RCP as a sustainable SCM within a construction and demolition waste (CDW). Rangel et al. [11] suggest that due to its physical and chemical characteristics, RCP can be used as an auxiliary material in cement. He et al. [12] found that up to 30% replacement of Portland cement with ultrafine RCP ($D_{50}=2.3\mu\text{m}$) could equal or even improve the mechanical strength of the reference paste. Kim and Jang [13] point out that the use of 10% RCP reaches 95% of the reference mechanical strength, and 20% RCP can achieve the target strength. Oliveira et al. [14] recommend that a replacement of up to 25% can be viable in mortars and concretes without affecting their mechanical properties, considering it a sustainable material.

Although RCP can be used to replace Portland cement, substitution rates are low and RCP sources, e.g., demolition [8,10,12] and laboratory [4,14,15], have not been compared. The objective of this study is to compare two sources of RCP (demolition and laboratory) in the mechanical properties of cement pastes. For this, Portland cement was substituted in percentages of 10, 20, and 30% by RCP. The workability of the pastes was studied by means of the mini-slump test; the modulus of elasticity was evaluated at 28 days; compressive strength was analyzed at 7 and 28 days, and the microstructure of the pastes was analyzed at 28 days.

2. Materials and methods

The cement used was a CP II-F32 from Lafarge Holcim, classified as ASTM type II according to ASTM C150 [16]. Two sources of RCP were used: a) demolition of a hospital in Rio de Janeiro (RCP-D) and residues of concrete samples tested in the laboratory (RCP-LAB). The RCP went through a sieving process and the material that passed the #100 sieve, maximum size of 150 μm , was selected. Subsequently, in order to achieve a granulometry close to Portland cement, a metal ball mill was used for 30 minutes.

By means of X-ray fluorescence (Shimadzu EDX-720 spectrometer) the chemical composition of the materials was established. The loss on ignition (LOI) was calculated using the procedures of NBR NM 18 [17]. The density of the materials was quantified using a helium pycnometer. The particle size was established through laser diffraction and the specific surface area (SSA) was calculated following ASTM C204 [18] standard.

The pastes were molded with a water-cement ratio of 0.4. Portland cement was replaced in three percentages by RCP (by weight): 10, 20, and 30%, in addition to the reference. Table 1 presents the mixtures analyzed and the proportions of the materials.

Workability was measured using the mini-slump test, considering the average of four measurements per mixture. The compressive strength was established at the age of 7 and 28 days using a Shimadzu UH-F (100 kN), with four specimens per mixture. The modulus of elasticity was determined at 28 days, according to ASTM C469 [19], in which the longitudinal displacement was measured using electrical transducers (LVDT). Finally, the microstructure of the pastes at 28 days was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (Hitachi TM3000).

The results were statistically evaluated by an analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey test for a significance of 0.05.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Materials properties

The chemical composition of the materials is detailed in Figure 1. The largest component of Portland cement is CaO, followed by SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃. Regarding the loss on ignition (LOI), this was 11.78%, which is within the recommendations for the type of cement (CP II - F), according to NBR 16697 [20]. The RCP has a lower content of CaO and a higher content of SiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃, in relation to cement; however, the sum of these components does not reach 70% and the LOI is greater than 4.5% to comply with ASTM C618 [21] to be within the pozzolanic material classification.

Table 1: Proportion of materials (by weight)

Mixture	Cement Portland	RCP-D	RCP-LAB
CP	100	-	-
D10	90	10	-
D20	80	20	-
D30	70	30	-
LAB10	90	-	10
LAB20	80	-	20
LAB30	70	-	30

Figure 1: Chemical composition of materials

The physical properties of the materials are described in Table 2. The grinding time was adequate to achieve a particle size close to that of Portland cement (D50). The RCP (D and LAB) have D10 and D90 values lower and higher than those of Portland cement, respectively. Regarding density, Portland cement has the highest density, followed by RCP-D and RCP-LAB. The specific surface is higher for RCP-D and RCP-LAB, in that order.

The morphology of the RCP-D and RCP-LAB particles is presented in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively. In both, crystalline particles can be observed, referring to the quartz present in the RCP, as well as hydration products, the latter both separately and adhered to larger particles.

Table 2: Physical properties of materials

Parameter	Cement Portland	RCP-D	RCP-LAB
D10 (μm)	2.06	1.77	1.71
D50 (μm)	14.14	13.19	13.82
D90 (μm)	47.79	57.23	62.49
Specific gravity (g/cm ³)	3.05	2.66	2.61
Specific surface area (cm ² /g)	3762.77	8614.72	7988.73

Figure 2: Morphology of the particles of a) RCP-D and b) RCP-LAB

3.2 Workability

The workability was expressed in spreading area (Figure 3). The results show that the greater the replacement of Portland cement by RCP, the workability decreases. The smallest reduction occurs for 10% of RCP, 20.38 and 22.76% for RCP-D and RCP-LAB, respectively. The maximum reduction occurs for pastes with 30% RCP, 43.10 and 48.42% for RCP-D and RCP-LAB, respectively. This negative trend is due to the morphology of the RCP particles (Figure 2) and their SSA (Table 2), increasing water requirement [7].

Figure 3: Spreading area

Through an ANOVA, it can be concluded that there are significant differences between the means of the mixtures (p value <0.05). The Tukey test established that the reference had greater workability than all the mixtures with RCP, regardless of the source. These results indicate that even 10% RCP had a significant negative influence on this property.

When the results between the two sources of RCP are compared by substitution percentage, it can be established that the results are statistically similar (p value >0.05). The p value for D10-LAB10, D20-LAB20 and D30-LAB30 were 0.615, 0.928 and 0.999, respectively. Therefore, the loss of workability is influenced by the substitution percentage and not by the RCP source. As observed in Figure 2, the morphology of the particles from both RCP sources was similar, in addition to their physical characteristics (Table 2); therefore, it can be expected that their influence on workability is the same, indicating a predominant physical effect of the RCP.

3.3 Compressive strength

The compressive strength of the pastes with RCP-D and RCP-LAB are presented in Figures 4a and 4b, respectively. For both sources, a negative trend is observed as Portland cement is replaced by RCP. In the case of RCP-D, for a substitution of 10%, the reduction is 5.13% and 3.11% for the ages of 7 and 28 days, respectively. The greatest reduction occurs for the substitution of 30%, with 31.40% and 20.76% for the ages of 7 and 28 days, respectively. The same behavior occurs for RCP-LAB; for a 10% substitution, the reduction is 2.25% and 3.56% for 7 and 28 days, respectively. For the case of 30% RCP, the decrease is 30.27% and 23.96% for 7 and 28 days, respectively. The negative effect on compressive strength is due to dilution effect of Portland cement and the low reactivity of the RCP particles [5,13].

Figure 4: Compressive strength for a) RCP-D and b) RCP-LAB

By ANOVA and Tukey test it is concluded that there are differences between the mixtures (p value <0.05). As previously mentioned, there are small differences between the reference and 10% RCP, regardless of the source, being similar for 7 days and 28 days. The results indicate that up to 10% replacement of Portland cement by RCP has no influence on this property. In the comparison between the results of RCP-C and RCP-LAB, it is observed that the results are similar, with a p value >0.05 for both ages and all substitution percentages. The p value for 7 days of the D10-LAB10, D20-LAB20 and D30-LAB30 mixtures was 0.844, 0.879 and 0.998, respectively. While, for 28 days, the p value of D10-LAB10, D20-LAB20 and D30-LAB30 was 0.999, 0.144 and 0.121, respectively. Therefore, the RCP source does not have a direct influence

on this property, although they differ in their chemical composition; the results show that most of the RCP components are inert, demonstrating predominantly a physical rather than a chemical effect.

3.4 Modulus of elasticity

Figure 5 presents the values of the modulus of elasticity of the pastes. As with the compression strength, a tendency to decrease is observed with the increase in the content of RCP-C and RCP-LAB. It has been established that there are significant differences between the tested samples (p value < 0.05). According to the Tukey test, the modulus of elasticity of the mixtures with 10% RCP, regardless of the source, is equal to the reference (p value > 0.05), indicating that this percentage does not affect the modulus of elasticity. The decrease in the modulus of elasticity for high percentages (20 and 30%) can be attributed to the lower hardness and rigidity of the RCP particles and to the dilution effect [14].

Figure 5: Modulus of elasticity

When comparing the results between both sources of RCP, it can be established that there are no differences in the modulus of elasticity, corroborating the results of the previously analyzed properties. The p value for D10-LAB10, D20-LAB20, and D30-LAB30 were 0.961, 1, and 0.999, respectively.

3.5 Microstructure

Figures 6 shows the microstructure of the pastes with 10, 20 and 30% RCP. It is observed that in all the pastes, hydration products were generated: hydrated calcium silicate (C-S-H), ettringite (AFt) and calcium hydroxide (CH), attributing that the RCP does not influence the formation of the different types of hydration products, but reduces the quantity.

Figure 6: Microstructure of a) D10, b) D20 c) D30, d) LAB10, e) LAB20, and f) LAB30

For 10% RCP pastes, there is the formation of traditional products with a relatively dense microstructure. Additionally, the presence of RCP covered by hydration products is observed, indicating a nucleation and filling effect in the cement matrix, characteristics that maintained the mechanical strength (Figure 4). In the case of pastes with 20 and 30% RCP, a loose microstructure is observed, especially for 30% RCP, explaining the significant reduction in compressive strength and modulus of elasticity.

4. Conclusions

An experimental investigation was conducted to assess the use of two sources of RCP: demolition and laboratory. Cement pastes were made with RCP as a replacement of Portland cement, leading to the following conclusions:

The RCP, regardless of the source, yielded the same results in the evaluated properties, indicating that, although this material can be considered heterogeneous due to its physical and chemical characteristics, it is composed of inert material, acting more like a filler. The morphology and SSA of the RCP particles reduce the workability (increase in water requirement), indicating a negative trend with increasing RCP.

The compressive strength was compromised with the inclusion of RCP, particularly at high percentages (30%), which can be attributed to the formation of fewer hydration products (dilution effect); however, 10% RCP did not significantly affect this property. The modulus of elasticity also exhibited similar behavior, with a non-significant reduction for 10% of RCP, indicating that the use of RCP would be feasible up to this percentage. The microstructure revealed the formation of hydration products in the pastes with RCP: C-S-H, CH, and AFt; however, a loose microstructure may become evident as the RCP content increases.

References

- [1] Boudali, S., Abdulsalam, B., Rafiean, A. H., Poncet, S., Soliman, A. and ElSafty, A., 'Influence of fine recycled concrete powder on the compressive strength of self-compacting concrete (SCC) using artificial neural network', *Sustainability* **13** (6) (2021) 3111.
- [2] Habert, G., Miller, S.A., John, V.M., Provis, J.L., Favier, A., Horvath, A. and Scrivener, K.L., 'Environmental impacts and decarbonization strategies in the cement and concrete industries', *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* **1** (11) (2020) 559-573.
- [3] de Brito, J. and Kurda, R., 'The past and future of sustainable concrete: A critical review and new strategies on cement-based materials', *J. Clean. Prod.* **281** (2021) 123558.

- [4] Cantero, B., Bravo, M., de Brito, J., Sáez del Bosque, I.F. and Medina, C., 'Thermal performance of concrete with recycled concrete powder as partial cement replacement and recycled CDW aggregate', *Appl. Sci.* **10** (13) (2020) 4540.
- [5] Liu, X., Liu, L., Lyu, K., Li, T., Zhao, P., Liu, R., Zuo, J., Fu, F. and Shah, S.P., 'Enhanced early hydration and mechanical properties of cement-based materials with recycled concrete powder modified by nanosilica', *J. Build. Eng.* **50** (2022) 104175.
- [6] Tang, Q., Ma, Z., Wu, H. and Wang, W., 'The utilization of eco-friendly recycled powder from concrete and brick waste in new concrete: A critical review', *Cem. Concr. Compos.* **114** (2020) 103807.
- [7] Cantero, B., Bravo, M., De Brito, J., del Bosque, I.S. and Medina, C., 'Mechanical behaviour of structural concrete with ground recycled concrete cement and mixed recycled aggregate', *J. Clean. Prod.* **275** (2020) 122913.
- [8] Xiao, J., Ma, Z., Sui, T., Akbarnezhad, A. and Duan, Z., 'Mechanical properties of concrete mixed with recycled powder produced from construction and demolition waste', *J. Clean. Prod.* **188** (2018) 720-731.
- [9] Kim, Y.J. and Choi, Y.W. 'Utilization of waste concrete powder as a substitution material for cement', *Constr. Build. Mater.* **30** (2012) 500-504.
- [10] Horsakulthai, V., 'Effect of recycled concrete powder on strength, electrical resistivity, and water absorption of self-compacting mortars', *Case Stud. Constr. Mater.* **15** (2021) e00725.
- [11] Rangel, C.S., Toledo Filho, R.D., Amario, M., Pepe, M., de Castro Polisseni, G. and de Andrade, G.P., 'Generalized quality control parameter for heterogenous recycled concrete aggregates: A pilot scale case study', *J. Clean. Prod.* **208** (2019) 589-601.
- [12] He, X., Zheng, Z., Yang, J., Su, Y., Wang, T. and Strnad, B., 'Feasibility of incorporating autoclaved aerated concrete waste for cement replacement in sustainable building materials', *J. Clean. Prod.* **250** (2020) 119455.
- [13] Kim, J. and Jang, H., 'Closed-loop recycling of C&D waste: Mechanical properties of concrete with the repeatedly recycled C&D powder as partial cement replacement', *J. Clean. Prod.* **343** (2022) 130977.
- [14] Oliveira, T.C., Dezen, B.G. and Possan, E., 'Use of concrete fine fraction waste as a replacement of Portland cement', *J. Clean. Prod.* **273** (2020) 123126.
- [15] Ma, Z., Yao, P., Yang, D. and Shen, J., 'Effects of fire-damaged concrete waste on the properties of its preparing recycled aggregate, recycled powder and newmade concrete', *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* **15** (2021) 1030-1045.
- [16] ASTM, 'ASTM C150/C150M-22: Standard Specification for Portland Cement', ASTM (West Conshohocken, 2022).
- [17] ABNT, 'NBR NM18: Cimento Portland - Análise química - Determinação de perda ao fogo', ABNT (Rio de Janeiro, 2012).
- [18] ASTM, 'ASTM C204: Standard Test Methods for Fineness of Hydraulic Cement by Air-Permeability Apparatus', ASTM (West Conshohocken, 2019).
- [19] ASTM, 'ASTM C469/C469M-22: Standard Test Method for Static Modulus of Elasticity and Poisson's Ratio of Concrete in Compression', ASTM (West Conshohocken, 2022).
- [20] ABNT, 'NBR 16697 - Cimento Portland Requisitos', ABNT (Rio de Janeiro, 2018).
- [21] ASTM, 'ASTM C618-22: Standard Specification for Coal Fly Ash and Raw or Calcined Natural Pozzolan for Use in Concrete', ASTM (West Conshohocken, 2022).